

Reversible high-temperature heat pumps/ORCs for flexible and economical geothermal projects: Bringing academic activities into the market via the FlexGeo project

Christopher Schifflechner¹, Jannik von Zabienski¹, Aaron Wesemann¹, Florian Kaufmann¹,
Dominik Geymann², Julius Sanders², Andreas Schuster², Tryfonas Roumpedakis³, Hartmut
Spliethoff¹

¹ Chair of Energy Systems, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich,
Boltzmannstr. 15, 85748 Garching, Germany

² Orcan Energy AG, Isarwinkel 14, 81379 München, Germany

³ Laboratory of Thermal Processes, School of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, 9
Heron Polytechniou, Zografou, 15780, Athens, Greece

c.schifflechner@tum.de

Keywords: High-temperature heat pump; Organic Rankine Cycle; Reversibility; Combined Heat and Power; District Heating

ABSTRACT

A key advantage of geothermal power generation is its reliability and base-load capability. However, the future energy system requires reliable energy sources that can also respond quickly to changes in demand. Reversible Organic Rankine Cycles (ORCs), which can also operate as high-temperature heat pumps (HTHPs), enable geothermal systems to operate more flexibly. Combined with a district heating system and/or heat storage systems (e.g. ATEs), reversible ORCs can react to the needs of the electricity grid and either produce electricity from the geothermal brine or consume power within the HTHP mode. Through the implementation of a storage system, the high-temperature heat produced during the HTHP operation can be used for increasing the geothermal power output at a later time.

This work provides an overview of the application potential of reversible ORCs for geothermal systems and their high flexibility capability. Furthermore, first experimental insights from a novel 20 kW_{el} reversible ORC test rig, which started operation in autumn 2024 at the Technical University of Munich will be presented. Finally, the work will present a potential roadmap for the market entry of the reversible ORC technology within the next years. In the framework of the European research project FlexGeo, a TRL 7 demonstrator of a reversible ORC will be developed and demonstrated at a real district heating network. The demonstrator, which is built by the modular ORC manufacturer ORCAN Energy, will have the capacity of a few hundred kW_{el} and will already represent the size of a future modular system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The future role of deep geothermal in the European energy sector is characterized by two main aspects: First, the increasing capacities of fluctuating renewable energy sources such as wind or PV result in a growing demand for reliable and efficient storage systems which can provide the required flexibility to the electric grid. Second, geothermal energy is mainly required as a potential backbone for the decarbonization of the European heating sector.

While in the past, one highlighted key advantage of geothermal heat and power generation was its reliability and base-load capability, research and industry are now focusing more and more on the flexibility potential of geothermal energy (Millstein et al. 2021). For example, the recent work by Ricks et al. (2024) studies the role of flexible Enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) in a decarbonized electricity system. The authors found for the western United States that a load-following generation combined with in-reservoir energy storage substantially increases the geothermal penetration and reduces bulk electricity supply costs compared to systems with inflexible EGSs. Also the developed “Flexible Geothermal Economics Modeling” tool FGEM by Aljubran und Horne (2024)) investigates several promising potential dispatch strategies, such as wellhead throttling and energy storage. Ricks et al. (2022) highlight the value of in-reservoir storage for flexible geothermal power, which can provide storage durations above 100 hours. Furthermore, also the combination of geothermal energy with district heating systems and heat pumps can be a promising approach to provide flexibility with geothermal energy (Liu et al. 2024).

Next to the focus on geothermal power generation, there is an increasing focus on the installation of large-scale high-temperature heat pumps (HTHP) in deep geothermal projects. Their purpose is the so-called capacity enhancement, meaning that the HTHP is used to cool down the geothermal brine further during the cold winter months in order to provide additional heat to the district heating network (Zosseder et al. 2023; Jeßberger et al. 2024). This can result in a complete or at least significant reduction of the fossil fuel peak load coverage. However, one main challenge of those systems is the low capacity factor of the installed HTHP, which can result in a potential challenging economic business case (Kaufmann et al. 2025).

As outlined in the following paper, the so-called reversible Organic Rankine cycle (ORC) / high-temperature heat pump (HTHP) can be a promising solution for future geothermal projects in order to enhance the flexibility potential of geothermal power generation and enhance the economic viability of large-scale geothermal HTHP systems. In the second half of the paper, recent results from a novel rev. ORC/HTHP test-rig as well as the potential future scale-up activities are presented.

2. THE REVERSIBLE HTHP/ORC TECHNOLOGY AND ITS POTENTIAL INTEGRATION IN GEOTHERMAL SYSTEMS

2.1 Technological concept of a reversible HTHP/ORC system

As the name reversible HTHP/ORC indicates, the technology concept combines a high-temperature heat pump on the one hand and an Organic Rankine Cycle on the other (Dumont et al. 2014). For geothermal applications in particular, the temperature requirements often exceed those of conventional heat pumps (Schlosser et al. 2020). For this reason, a high-temperature heat pump is required for use. The exact implementation of these two systems in one system is shown in Figure 1. The ORC contains four major components. Two of these are heat exchangers. In the evaporator, the working medium is converted from a liquid state to a superheated vapor state by means of heat input. The vapor is then expanded to a low pressure level in the turbine, thereby extracting work from the system in the form of electrical energy. After the turbine, the vapor is condensed in the second heat exchanger and heat is dissipated at a significantly lower temperature level than previously supplied in the evaporator. In the last process step of the cycle, the

liquid working medium is pumped back up to a higher pressure level before it re-enters the evaporator. A significant advantage of the ORC in contrast to conventional Rankine cycles is that the organic working medium has a significantly lower boiling temperature compared to water and is therefore ideal for the use of low temperature heat or geothermal excess heat.

While the ORC system is a right-hand process and can convert low-temperature heat into electricity, the operation of the HTHP system is left-hand controlled. This means that the heat is pumped from a lower temperature level to a higher temperature level by using electricity. As shown in figure 1, the heat pump also contains two heat exchangers for the evaporation and condensation of the working medium.

However, in HTHP mode, the heat is supplied to the system at a significantly lower temperature level. Following evaporation, the vapour is compressed, which leads to an increase in temperature. A compressor is therefore required for the heat pump instead of the turbine. The heat can then be released at a higher temperature level than that supplied in the condenser. After condensation, the working medium passes through a throttle instead of a pump. As a result, the temperature of the medium is reduced to a lower temperature level, in parallel with a reduction in pressure. In the next step, the working medium can absorb heat again in the evaporator. The ratio of power used to useful heat can be described by the coefficient of performance (COP).

Both systems are combined by interconnecting them using three-way valves so that the heat exchangers can be used for both operating modes with the same function. An innovation in the technology is the reversible twin-screw compressor, which can be operated as a compressor and expander. This means that only a throttle needs to be integrated in addition to the feed pump.

This reversible HTHP/ORC approach exhibits an operational range of twice its nominal capacity being able to provide either electricity during times of excess heat or to further utilize the geothermal brine return in case of an insufficient geothermal heat supply or peak load heat demands. To further demonstrate the potential of such HTHP/ORC systems, three application scenarios are characterised in the following.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the reversible HTHP/ORC technology, illustrating the integrated configuration of an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and a High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP) within a single system architecture.

2.2 Application scenario 1: Varying heat demand an established DHS – solving the dilemma of the low capacity factors

While the demand for heat is subject to seasonal fluctuations high heat demand in winter and low heat demand in summer geothermal energy is referred to as

the climate-neutral base load. The reason for this is the constant supply of heat throughout the year. One way to solve this dilemma is to use an HTHP/ORC system. Figure 2 illustrates this more explicitly (Kaufmann et al. 2022).

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the reversible HTHP/ORC technology, illustrating the integrated configuration of an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and a High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP) within a single system architecture.

The proposed concept enhances system flexibility by utilizing a High-Temperature Heat Pump (HTHP) to cover peak heat demands, thereby reducing or even substituting the need for a gas-fired peak load boiler. During periods of low heat demand, when geothermal capacity exceeds consumption, the surplus heat can be effectively utilized by an Organic Rankine Cycle

(ORC) for additional energy recovery. This approach is particularly advantageous when the heat demand profile ensures a sufficient number of operating hours for both the HTHP and ORC, supporting economic viability. However, in cases with insufficient operating hours, continued partial use of the gas boiler may be necessary to maintain cost-effectiveness.

2.3 Application scenario 2: Expanding DHS – solving the dilemma between sufficient heat for the ORC and a fast DHS expansion

The second application scenario deals with the expansion of a district heating system for geothermal projects with a brine temperature of e.g. at least 100°C. While a sole heating project would face the challenge of very low revenues during the first years due to small heat demand, the raising heat demand decreases the available heat for a potential ORC system if a conventional ORC is installed as part of a geothermal combined heat and power project (Eyerer et al. 2020). On top of that the roll out and implementation of a district heating system is linked with a high upfront investment. To further guarantee a safe investment the use of an ORC in the first years thus is not neglectable, yet after some years the use of a heat pump or gas boiler to cover the peak load demands gets mandatory. As a solution to this dilemma a reversible ORC/HTHP is a highly promising approach.

Figure 3; Typical expansion scenario of a geothermal greenfield district heating project.

2.4 Application scenario 3: Flexibility enhancement – solving the dilemma of high electricity prices during dark doldrums

Another possibility to react to the electricity market and adjust the operational mode to the current electricity prices. Especially if the reversible HTHP/ORC system is coupled either with a small surface buffer heat storage or even a large-scale UTES system, the rev. system can operate as an HTHP to charge the storage system during periods with very low or even negative electricity prices and boost the power production during periods with high electricity market prices. This would enable higher revenue streams for the geothermal plant, since low electricity prices can be used to store extra heat at a high temperature level, and periods with high electricity prices are used to achieve higher incomes.

Figure 4; Potential operational modes of a rev. ORC/HTHP system depending on the fluctuating electricity prices.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DEMONSTRATION

The reversible ORC test rig was constructed at TUM over the last years and started its operation in the middle of 2024. In the following section the test rig will be described and results of the first successful experimental campaigns will be given.

3.1 Test rig description

The following Figure 5 shows a picture of the reversible ORC test rig at the Technical University of Munich without insulation on the significant components. On the upper left side, the reversible 20 kW_{mech} twin-screw machine coupled to a synchronous reluctance motor can be observed. The working fluid used is the synthetic low-GWP refrigerant R1233zd(E), which is characterized by a low Global Warming Potential (GWP) compared to conventional working fluids, such as R245fa (Heberle et al. 2016).

Figure 5: Picture of the rev. ORC test rig at TUM without insulation.

Figure 5 shows a simplified P&ID of the test rig highlighting the two individual operation modes as well as the corresponding control loops. The test rig is supplied by a 200 kW_{th} hot water heating circuit, which serves as heat source and simulates the geothermal brine. Additionally, a closed-loop intermediate cooling

circuit (ICC) allows simulating a district heating network (DHN). In HTHP mode the reversible machine is operated as compressor and therefore compressing working fluid to achieve higher temperature levels by adding electrical power. The high-temperature heat is then transferred to the ICC where corresponding mass flows of the cooling water can be adjusted. With that, thermal outputs can be easily set. A throttle valve expands the working fluid in order to absorb low-temperature heat and close the thermodynamic cycle. In ORC mode the machine is operated as expander, generating electrical power via a coupled generator.

The heat source supplies heat at elevated temperature levels up to 140 °C. A working fluid pump adjusts mass flows and pressurizes the system. In both operation modes the two main heat exchangers (HEX) keep their nature. Evaporator will in both modes stay the unit of heat input and condenser for heat output. This is mainly due to the given parallels to real-life applications in geothermal plants, where it cannot be switched between a HEX in contact with geothermal suspension to a HEX coupled to a DHN.

Figure 6: Simplified P&ID of the constructed reversible ORC test rig with parts of the heating circuit. Main control loops for ORC (red) and HTHP (blue) operation.

3.2 Experimental results

In the first months of operation initial experimental campaigns were conducted mainly focusing on energetic efficiencies such as coefficient of performance (COP) in HTHP mode and thermal efficiency ($\eta_{th,el,net}$) in ORC mode. Here, the COP gives the ratio of supplied heat into the DHN to the electrical power consumed by the compressor. In contrast, $\eta_{th,el,net}$ gives the ratio between the net generated electrical power - supplied to the electrical grid - to the thermal input by the geothermal brine.

To assess the performance of the system, multiple parameters were varied in the entire study. Both modes were analysed independently from each other with focus on their individual performance indicators. In

HTHP mode, two approaches were chosen - an application-based and lift dependent approach. In this work it is mainly focused on the lift-dependent approach since high temperature lifts with efficient COP are favourable. Here, the heat source temperature was held constant at 75 °C while adjusting the DHN return temperature, holding a constant temperature spread of 10 K. The DHN mass flow rate was adjusted between 0.5 kg/s, 1.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg. For a detailed description of the experimental methodology, the reader is invited to have a look into the publication of Kaufmann et al. 2024. Figure 7 visualizes the corresponding results for COP over temperature lift (ΔT_{lift}). Here, the temperature lift is defined as the difference between the saturation temperatures of the

working fluid at condensation and evaporation pressure.

Figure 7: COP over temperature lift for given operation conditions (adapted from Kaufmann et al. 2024)

It can be seen that for rising temperature lifts the COP decreases. Values from 6.5 to 3 could be achieved for temperature lifts from 25 K to 57 K. These findings show similar values to comparable heat pump applications in research and industry (Arpagaus et al. 2018; Schlosser et al. 2020; Weitzer et al. 2025).

For the ORC analysis, hot water mass flow rates were adjusted (0.5 kg/s, 1.0 kg/s and 1.5 kg) while the supply temperature was set at either 110 °C or 130 °C, marking real application conditions. The evaporation pressure was tested at different levels while holding condensation pressure constant. The working fluid pump speed was varied at 25%, 35% and 45% of its maximum achievable capacity of 1800 rpm. Higher pump speeds were not possible due to strong vibrations of the pump, restricting mass flow to a certain limit. Figure 8 shows the results of the thermal efficiency over the pressure ratio over expansion ($r_{p,\text{exp}}$) only for a heating circuit mass flow rate of 1.0 kg/s to match the scope of this work.

Figure 8: Thermal efficiency over pressure ratio for given operation conditions (adapted from Kaufmann et al. 2024))

It can be observed that, depending on pressure ratio and pump speed, the thermal efficiency strongly varies. For the highest pump speeds and optimum pressure ratios, the highest thermal efficiencies of approximately 5% to 6% can be achieved. Maximum efficiencies for

pressure ratios between 3 and 3.5 match the built-in volume ratio of the expander of 3.1.

The findings indicate efficient operation of the reversible ORC without any significant losses in performance of one operation mode. This builds a strong base for the further development of reversible ORC systems.

4. CONCLUSIONS & OUTLOOK

The present work exhibits three promising operational and application modes of a reversible ORC/HTHP system. Furthermore, promising recent experimental results from a novel test rig are presented, demonstrating the technical viability of the technology. During the next months, further improvement measures, especially addressing the lubrication oil management system, will be carried out. It is expected that those adaptations will further increase the performance indicators in both operational modes further and provide valuable insights for the scale-up of the technology.

In the framework of the European research project FlexGeo, a TRL 7 demonstrator of a reversible ORC will be developed and demonstrated at a real district heating network. The demonstrator, which is built by the modular ORC manufacturer ORCAN Energy, will have the capacity of a few hundred kWel and will already represent the size of a future modular system.

Acknowledgements

Funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101147576 (FlexGeo) is gratefully acknowledged. The information presented on this document reflects only the authors' view. The funding agencies are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

REFERENCES

- Aljbran, M. J.; Horne, R. N. (2024): Fgem: Flexible Geothermal Economics Modeling Tool. In: *Applied Energy* 353, S. 122125. Doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122125.
- Arpagaus, Cordin; Bless, Frédéric; Uhlmann, Michael; Schiffmann, Jürg; Bertsch, Stefan S. (2018): High temperature heat pumps: Market overview, state of the art, research status, refrigerants, and application potentials. In: *Energy* 152, S. 985–1010. DOI: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.166.
- Dumont, Olivier; Quoilin, Sylvain; Lemort, Vincent (2014): Design, Modeling and Experimentation of a Reversible HP-ORC Prototype. In: Volume 3B: Oil and Gas Applications; Organic Rankine Cycle Power Systems; Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles; Wind Energy. ASME Turbo Expo 2014: Turbine Technical Conference and Exposition. Düsseldorf, Germany, 16.06.2014 - 20.06.2014: American Society of Mechanical Engineers.

- Eyerer, Sebastian; Schifflechner, Christopher; Hofbauer, Sebastian; Bauer, Wolfgang; Wieland, Christoph; Spliethoff, Hartmut (2020): Combined heat and power from hydrothermal geothermal resources in Germany: An assessment of the potential. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 120, S. 109661. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.109661.
- Heberle, Florian; Schifflechner, Christopher; Brüggemann, Dieter (2016): Life cycle assessment of Organic Rankine Cycles for geothermal power generation considering low-GWP working fluids. In: *Geothermics* 64, S. 392–400. DOI: 10.1016/j.geothermics.2016.06.010.
- Jeßberger, Jaromir; Heberle, Florian; Brüggemann, Dieter (2024): Maximising the potential of deep geothermal energy: Thermal output increase by large-scale heat pumps. In: *Applied Thermal Engineering* 257, S. 124240. DOI: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.124240.
- Kaufmann, Florian; Schifflechner, Christopher; Wieland, Christoph; Spliethoff, Hartmut (2022): Techno-Economic Evaluation of reversible Organic Rankine Cycles in geothermal combined Heat and Power Plants. In: *Ecos 2022 - The 35th International Conference On Efficiency, Cost, Optimization, Simulation and Environmental Impact of Energy Systems*.
- Kaufmann, Florian; Spliethoff, Hartmut; Schifflechner, Christopher (2025): Reversible High-Temperature Heat Pumps for Peak Load Coverage in Geothermal Heating Plants: A Techno-Economic Analysis: Preprint submitted to *Energy Conversion and Management*. Online verfügbar unter https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5153108.
- Kaufmann, Florian; Zabienski, Jannik von; Ribbeck, Leon von; Ehmann, Moritz; Spliethoff, Hartmut; Schifflechner, Christopher (2024): Experimental Analysis of a Reversible High-Temperature Heat Pump/Orc Test Rig for Geothermal Chp Applications.
- Liu, Dong-xi; Lei, Hai-Yan; Li, Jia-Shu; Dai, Chuan-shan; Xue, Rui; Liu, Xin (2024): Optimization of a district heating system coupled with a deep open-loop geothermal well and heat pumps. In: *Renewable Energy* 223, S. 119991. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2024.119991.
- Millstein, Dev; Dobson, Patrick; Jeong, Seongeun (2021): The Potential to Improve the Value of U.S. Geothermal Electricity Generation Through Flexible Operations. In: *Journal of Energy Resources Technology* 143 (1), Artikel 010905. DOI: 10.1115/1.4048981.
- Ricks, Wilson; Voller, Katharine; Galban, Gerame; Norbeck, Jack H.; Jenkins, Jesse D. (2024): The role of flexible geothermal power in decarbonized electricity systems. In: *Nat Energy*. DOI: 10.1038/s41560-023-01437-y.
- Schlosser, F.; Jesper, M.; Vogelsang, J.; Walmsley, T. G.; Arpagaus, C.; Hesselbach, J. (2020): Large-scale heat pumps: Applications, performance, economic feasibility and industrial integration. In: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 133, S. 110219. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2020.110219.
- Weitzer, Maximilian; Reiß, Sabine; Steger, Daniel; Kolb, Sebastian; Karl, Jürgen (2025): Experimental characterization of a reversible heat pump – Organic Rankine cycle pilot plant as a thermally integrated Carnot battery. In: *Applied Thermal Engineering* 260, S. 124872. DOI: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.124872.
- Zosseder, Kai; Haas, C.; Schifflechner, C.; Chicco, Jessica Maria; Hajto, Marek; Cipala, B. et al. (2023): Scenario Catalogue - Integration of Geothermal Energy into District Heating and Cooling Networks. Public Deliverable of the SAPHEA Project. Online verfügbar unter https://www.cee.ed.tum.de/fileadmin/w00cbe/hydro/Pictures/pic_projects/SAPHEA/SAPHEA_Scenario_Catalogue.pdf.